

Electrometric Studies on the Compositions of Thorium Polyvanadates

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The formation and composition of thorium polyvanadates, obtained by the interaction of thorium salt and different alkali vanadates (ortho, pyro, meta, and poly) have been investigated by means of glass electrode and conductometric titrations between the reactants at different pH levels in aqueous solutions, each of the reagent alternatively being used as titrant. The sharp breaks and inflections in titration curves provide definite evidence of the formation and precipitation of thorium orthovanadate and pyrovanadate, having the compositions $3\text{ThO}_2 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{ThO}_2 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at pH ranges 7.5-6.0 and 6.0-4.8, respectively. The precipitation of thorium orthovanadate is almost quantitative and the titrations offer a simple means of determining thorium in solutions at suitable concentrations and pH ranges.

In an earlier communication¹, the reaction between thorium salt and vanadate poly-anions by amperometric techniques was reported. In this investigation, efforts have been made to substantiate the earlier results by other electrometric methods, involving pH and conductometric titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalR (B.D.H.) reagents, vanadium pentoxide, sodium hydroxide, and thorium nitrate, and reagent grade HCl were used and their solutions prepared in air-free conductivity water.

A standard solution of sodium orthovanadate was prepared by dissolving a requisite quantity of V_2O_5 in the calculated amount of boiling solution of NaOH of required strength; alkali pyro- and meta-vanadate solutions were then prepared by the action of requisite quantities of HCl at 100°.

As no electrode, reversible to Th^{4+} ions, is known, potentiometric titrations could not be carried out and the course of reaction between Th^{4+} and alkali vanadate solutions was followed by measuring the change in H^+ -ion concentration.

Glass Electrode Titrations.—pH of the solutions were measured with a Cambridge null-deflection type pH-meter; glass electrode of the range 0-13 pH, calibrated frequently by buffer solutions of different pH values, was used in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode, connected to the cell by agar-KCl bridge. The titre solution (20 ml) was taken in the cell each time and stirred electrically. The observed pH values were plotted against the volume of the titrant added; from the sharp inflection in titration curves and maximum values of $d\text{pH}/dV$, the end-point was determined.

Conductometric Titrations.—The conductance of the solutions was measured on a Kohlrausch Universal Bridge, using A. F. Generator as a source of a.c.. The solution (20 ml) was taken in the cell each time and kept immersed in an electrically maintained thermostat. The conductance values, after being corrected for dilution effect, were plotted against the volume of the titrant added and the end point was located graphically.

The same strengths of the solutions were employed in both the techniques for the sake of comparison of results. The results of electrometric studies are summarised in Table I. Only two representative graphs (Fig. 1 and 2) illustrating direct and reverse *pH* and conductometric titrations of ortho- and pyro-vanadates, respectively, have been shown for the sake of brevity.

TABLE I

Molarity of solutions.		Equivalence points (ml).		
Th (NO ₃) ₄ .	3Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Calc.	Observed from	
			Max. <i>dpH/dV</i> .	Conductance.
Orthovanadate:				
Direct titrations (Fig. 1, curves ID & IID).				
<i>M</i> /10	<i>M</i> /75	4.00	3.98	4.00
<i>M</i> /25	<i>M</i> /200	3.75	3.74	3.80
<i>M</i> /50	<i>M</i> /450	3.33	3.38	3.40
<i>M</i> /75	<i>M</i> /750	3.00	2.95	3.10
Reverse titrations (Fig. 1, curves IR & IIR).				
<i>M</i> /40	<i>M</i> /10	3.33	3.30	3.40
<i>M</i> /100	<i>M</i> /30	4.00	3.98	4.00
<i>M</i> /250	<i>M</i> /70	3.73	3.70	3.70
<i>M</i> /450	<i>M</i> /100	2.95	3.02	3.05
2 Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ . Pyrovanadate:				
Direct titrations (Fig. 2, curves ID & IID).				
<i>M</i> /10	<i>M</i> /60	3.33	3.32	3.35
<i>M</i> /30	<i>M</i> /150	4.00	4.04	4.05
<i>M</i> /60	<i>M</i> /350	3.45	3.48	3.50
<i>M</i> /80	<i>M</i> /600	3.20	3.25	3.10
Reverse titrations (Fig. 2, curves IR & IIR).				
<i>M</i> /100	<i>M</i> /20	4.00	4.02	4.00
<i>M</i> /250	<i>M</i> /40	3.20	3.24	3.20
<i>M</i> /400	<i>M</i> /60	3.00	2.95	3.05
<i>M</i> /600	<i>M</i> /100	3.33	3.38	3.40

DISCUSSION

Saxena and Mittal¹⁻³ have shown that additions of HCl to sodium orthovanadate and NaOH to V₂O₅ solutions at the room temperature cause the formation of various poly-anions of uncertain compositions, but when the solution is heated after each addition of the reagent, the three different vanadates, viz., pyro-Na₄V₂O₇, meta-NaVO₃, and poly-Na₂O.2.5V₂O₅, are formed in the vicinity of *pH* 10.0, 7.0, and 4.5, respectively. It was

2. *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1955, 40, 108.

3. *Idem, Naturwiss.*, 1954, 51, 102.

therefore considered of interest to ascertain whether similar salts of heavy metals may be precipitated as a result of metathesis. A series of reactions between thorium nitrate and each of these alkali vanadates has therefore been studied by electrometric techniques involving glass electrode and conductometric titrations with regard to the changes occurring in H^+ -ion concentrations and compositions of the precipitates formed.

Orthovanadate Titrations.—The pH s of $Th(NO_3)_4$ and orthovanadate solutions were measured by a glass electrode and found to be in the vicinity of 2.80 and 11.50, respectively. Fig. 1 (curves ID and IR) illustrates the changes occurring in H^+ -ion concentrations when thorium nitrate solutions are treated with Na-orthovanadate solutions. In direct titrations (curve ID), when thorium salt solution was added from the microburette to alkali orthovanadate solution, a gradual decrease in pH was observed till at the stoichiometric end

point (the stage at which the reaction ends if simple double decomposition takes place); a sharp fall in pH was noted with the inflection corresponding to the molar ratio of $ThO_2 : V_2O_5$ as 3 : 2, suggesting the formation of lemon-yellow thorium orthovanadate, $3ThO_2 \cdot 2V_2O_5$, in the pH range 7.5-6.0. In the case of reverse titrations (curve IR), when orthovanadate solution was used as the titrant, the pH first increased slowly up to the addition of about half the amount of titrant required for complete reaction and then sharply; at the stoichiometric end point, a marked jump in pH was observed, suggesting the formation of the same compound according to the equation:

Employing similar concentrations of the reactants, both the direct and reverse conductometric titrations were carried out (curves IID & IIR, Fig. 1). The titration curves yield well-defined breaks at the stoichiometric end-point corresponding to the molar ratio of $ThO_2 : V_2O_5$ as 3:2 and confirm formation of the identical compound, thorium orthovanadate, $3ThO_2 \cdot 2V_2O_5$.

Pyrovanadate Titrations.—Alkali pyrovanadate solutions were prepared as usual and their reaction with thorium salt solutions was studied by glass-electrode and conductometric titrations. The direct titration curves (Fig. 2, curve ID) are similar to those of orthovanadate titrations except that, initially in the latter case, the pH falls more rapidly but gradually; at the stoichiometric end point, a sharp downward jump is obtained corresponding to the formation and precipitation of thorium pyrovanadate, having the molecular composition $ThO_2 \cdot V_2O_5$ in the pH range 6.0-4.8. Reverse titrations (Fig. 2, curve IR) also support the above results.

Employing similar strengths, both direct and reverse conductometric titrations between thorium nitrate and alkali pyrovanadate were carried out (Fig. 2, curves IID & IIR). In direct titrations, when $Th(NO_3)_4$ was used as the titrant (curve IID), the conductance values almost remained constant up to the addition of one mole of $Th(NO_3)_4$ per mole of pyrovanadate, after which a sharp rise in conductance was noticed. The well-defined breaks, obtained from the titration curves, suggest the formation of $ThO_2 \cdot V_2O_5$. In the case of reverse titrations (curve IIR), the conductance values increase appreciably from the beginning of the titration, which can be ascribed to the availability of free sodium and chloride ions present in pyrovanadate solution due to removal of one Na_2O mole/orthovanadate mole by addition of HCl . After completion of the reaction, conductance rises sharply and the break confirms the formation of the same compound. The reaction can be represented as:

Similarly the reactions between thorium salt and alkali meta- and poly-vanadate solutions have also been studied, but the curves do not exhibit any appreciable breaks and inflections. This may be ascribed to (i) the strong tendency of vanadate ions for polymerisation at lower pH (vanadate ion in the pH range 7-4 forms unstable poly-anions of

uncertain composition²⁻⁵) and in the case of polyvanadate, which exists in the vicinity of pH 4.5, small difference in the pH values of the reactants; (ii) the presence of $NaCl$ in appreciable amounts in both meta- and poly-vanadates, preventing the occurrence of breaks in the conductometric titration curves.

It is observed that after each addition of the titrant solution, it takes little time for the pH and conductance values to become steady. Thorough stirring in the vicinity of end point has a favourable effect. Each titration takes about half an hour for completion.

It is apparent from the electrometric study that the thorium salt with alkali ortho-

and pyro-vanadates yield corresponding salts by metathesis, namely, $3\text{ThO}_2 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{ThO}_2 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$, at pH range 7.5-6.0 and 6.0-4.8, respectively. The results of these investigations are in full conformity with those obtained from amperometric study¹.

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